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Characteristics of the Analysis of the External Environment in the Process of the Developing a Strategy for the Development of Commercial Banks

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1. Introduction.

Analyzing the external environment of bank activity is one of the necessary activities at all stages of the development strategy development process. The process of researching the external environment requires the organization of three components: the external environment, the immediate surrounding environment and the internal environment of the bank.

2. Methodology

The analysis of the external environment is a process, with the help of which the factors external to the bank that form the strategic plan are made. Analysis of external environment includes economic, legal coordination and management, political processes, natural environment and resources, social and cultural aspects of society, scientific-technical and technological development of society, infrastructure, etc. It helps to get very important results. It gives the bank some time to anticipate opportunities, plan for contingencies, create a structure to quickly eliminate potential risks, and develop strategies that turn risks into desirable opportunities.

3. Result and discussion

To study the external environment of banks, seven areas are usually defined: economy, politics, market, technology, legal coordination, international situation and social situation.

Economic factors. The current and projected state of the economy can dramatically affect an organization's goals. Some factors of the external economic environment need to be constantly diagnosed and evaluated. The analysis of the economic components of the macro environment provides an opportunity to understand how resources are formed and distributed. The organization of the a number of indicators: GDP volume, inflation rate, unemployment rate, interest rates, labor

productivity, tax rates, balance of payments, savings norms, etc. During the organization of economic components, it is very important to pay attention to such factors as the general level of economic development, the availability of natural resources, climate, the level and type of competitive relations, the structure of the population, the qualifications of the workforce and the amount of wages.

Political factors. The analysis in this direction leads to the formation of a clear understanding of the goals and priorities of state bodies from the point of view of the development of society, as well as the tools used in the implementation of the state's own policy.

Market factors. Volatile market risk is an area of serious concern for a bank. Factors that can directly affect the bank's success or failure are analyzed within the analysis of the market sector.

Technological factors. Analysis in this direction helps to identify the opportunities opened by science for the development of new goods and services or modernization of existing ones.

International factors. Risks and opportunities may arise due to changes in the availability of raw materials the activities of foreign cartels, the exchange rate and the political situation in the countries that are emerging as investment objects or markets.

Legal factors. Study of laws and other regulatory documents, state of the legal system.

Social factors. People's attitude to work and quality of life traditions and religious views, demographic structure, values, population growth rates, tali level, etc. With the help of the analysis of the external environment, the bank can create a list of risks and opportunities that may be faced in this environment. The most common methods of monitoring the state of the external environment include: mass media, books and other informative study and analysis of materials published in publications;

- ✓ Participation in professional conferences;
- ✓ Analysis of the organization's experience;
- ✓ Studying the opinion of the employees of organization;
- ✓ Conducting meetings and exchange of ideas within the organization.
- ✓ Organize the immediate ambient environment is analyzed for the following main components:
 - ✓ Buyers;
 - ✓ Suppliers;
 - ✓ Competitors;
 - ✓ Labor market.

In the direction of buyers, their geographical location, demographic and socio-psychological characteristics, and the attitude of buyers to the product are analyzed. The buyer's bargaining power is the level of information ownership, the volume of purchases, the relationship between the seller and the buyer, the availability of similar products in the market, the amount of time and money that can be spent for the buyer to switch to another seller, as well as his sensitivity to price changes.

During the evaluation of the suppliers, it is proposed to examine the value of the delivered goods, quality guarantee, unconditional fulfillment of the terms of the contract by the supplier depends on the following factors:

- level of specialization of the supplier;

- cost of attracting other customers;
- of the buyer when purchasing certain resources degree of specialization;
- concentration of the supplier to work with separate customers;
- the importance of the sales volume for the supplier.

During competitor analysis their strengths and weaknesses are identified. Analysis of the labor market, suitable labor for the bank availability of resources, opportunities to attract them and focuses on identifying other.

The analysis of the internal environment is directed to the discovery of the potential that the organization can rely on during the competitive struggle in the process of achieving its goals. The internal environment is analyzed in the following direction:

- ✓ Bank employees, their potential, qualifications, interests, etc.
- ✓ Organization of management.
- ✓ Taking into account production, organizational, operational and technical, technological factors and scientific research and development;
- ✓ Financial resources of the bank;
- ✓ Marketing;
- ✓ Organizational culture;

4. Conclusion

As conclusion it is necessary to recognize that the analysis of the external environment is carried out continuously, and on this basis, the information that is the basis for the assessment of the current and strategic situation of the bank is obtained.

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